

STUDY OF THE ENERGY ABSORPTION CAPABILITY OF SANDWICH STRUCTURES WITH FOAM CORE AND CFRP FACE SHEETS

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Keywords: Sandwich structures, Finite elements, Energy absorption, CFRP, Polymeric foams

ABSTRACT

Sandwich panels made of advanced composite skins and lightweight cores have potential uses as efficient crash members in vehicle structures. The assessment of the energy absorption capability of these structures is of major relevance during the design phase, so it would be beneficial to be able to predict their behaviour under complex loading conditions, including impact scenarios. Hence, the aim of this investigation was to study the ability of Finite Element Analysis to estimate the response of complex sandwich structures subjected to mixed-mode loading conditions at quasi-static rates. A set of experimental tests were conducted and good agreement was found between experimental and numerical results, in terms of load-displacement curves, energy absorption and failure modes. Furthermore, Finite Element Analysis was used to assess the extent of the interfacial failure between skin and core, which was not visible during the experimental tests, as well as the contribution of each individual component to the overall energy absorbed by the structure. The quasi-static results can be used as the basis for predicting the response of similar structures under impact conditions.

1 INTRODUCTION

Sandwich structures made of carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) skins and lightweight cores are widely used in the transportation industry to improve the efficiency of vehicles. In particular, polymeric foams are of increasing interest because of the large number of synthetic polymers which are available and their high energy absorption capability when loaded in compression. Therefore, a combination of CFRP and polymeric foam in a sandwich configuration can be used not only as a lightweight structural component but also as a passive safety device.

Since the cost of the constituent materials is high and the manufacturing of sandwich structures can be both complex and expensive, it would be beneficial to be able to predict the response of the components with a certain level of accuracy in order to reduce costs during prototype development. One way to do this is to use Finite Element Analysis (FEA). However, one of the major concerns regarding composite materials is capturing their performance under crushing conditions, due to the large number of variables which influence their response, including geometry, ply thickness, layup and the inclusion of different trigger mechanisms [1-5]. In addition, the combination of composites with other materials, such as polymeric foams, increases the complexity of the numerical models required, since the models need to incorporate not only the deformation of the core and skins but also the behavior of the interface between them, while applying appropriate failure criteria.

In this study, the aim is to investigate the performance of sandwich structures subjected to a mixed mode loading case at low (quasi-static) strain rates, with a view to assessing the accuracy of the results predicted by FE models created with the commercial package Abaqus [6-8].

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Polymeric foam was used as the core of a sandwich structure with CFRP face sheets. The core comprised blocks of foam separated by carbon fibre ribs through the thickness of the final sandwich

panel. The plies of the composite consisted of non-crimp fabrics as well as unidirectional laminae. The carbon fibre ribs were the result of the manufacturing process, in which three individual components (including the foam) were combined, as illustrated in Fig. 1. First of all, blocks of foam were wrapped in the “skin member 1”, which consisted of four plies. Then, three more plies (“skin member 2”) were laid up on each side of the component. Finally, the epoxy resin which bonded all the parts together was infused by Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM). The carbon fibre reinforced polymer ribs were then formed from contacting skins of adjacent foam blocks. This manufacturing process to create ribs was motivated by the desire to minimise the debonding between the core and the composite skin during loading conditions similar to a side-pole impact scenario from the automotive industry, while probably also adding other benefits such as extra stiffness and strength depending on the loading direction. The thickness of the foam core was 15 mm, whereas each composite face was 2.7 mm thick, resulting in a total thickness of 20.4 mm.

Figure 1: Schematic of the three different parts of the sandwich structure: foam, skin member 1 and skin member 2

The mechanical properties of the polymeric foam were determined in [9], conducting uniaxial tensile, uniaxial compression and shear punch tests. The properties of the CFRP were extracted from standard coupon tests in uniaxial tension [10] and uniaxial compression [11-12] of unidirectional and [0/90] laminates, as well as cyclic tensile tests [13] on a ± 45 laminate (both unidirectional and biaxial laminae).

2.2 Quasi-static tests on the sandwich structure

Motivated by the severe scenario of the side-pole impact test in the automotive industry, a reduced-scale quasi-static test was designed. The specimens were 140 mm \times 140 mm and they were fixed over the bottom 40 mm with a screw clamp and loaded by displacing a cylindrical steel pole with a diameter of 57 mm into the specimen. A schematic of the test set-up is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Schematic of the indentation test conducted on the sandwich structure

Since ribs were introduced along the structure, it was decided to study two different scenarios: (i) structure loaded directly on top of one rib located in the middle of the specimen, and (ii) the pole indenting the component in between two ribs. For each configuration, two samples were tested using a screw-driven Instron 5982 machine and the load-displacement response was measured with a 100 kN

load cell and the cross-head displacement respectively. All tests were conducted at 1 mm/min at room temperature.

2.3 Finite Element modelling of the sandwich structure

Numerical simulations were performed with Abaqus/Explicit (Abaqus 2017). The core was modelled with the “Crushable Foam” material model (using the methodology and input parameters from [9]), while “ABQ_PLY_FABRIC” was used for the parts made of carbon fibre. Even though the tests were conducted at quasi-static rates, the material model selected for the composite skins was only available in the explicit version of the FE package. Furthermore, the final aim was to create and validate a methodology that will allow the analysis of the response of similar structures under impact conditions. Solid hexahedral elements were used to model the polymeric foam, defined as C3D8R elements, including enhanced hourglass control to avoid zero-energy modes. The composite skins were modelled as conventional shells with S4R elements. The adhesion between the core and the “skin member 1” was defined with zero-thickness cohesive elements (COH3D8). In addition, to allow the model to predict delamination between composite plies, the epoxy resin was included in specific areas as more zero-thickness cohesive elements. Inputs for the cohesive zone traction-separation properties were provided by Bragnolo (private communication, 2018). Finally, the cylindrical pole was created as a rigid body and it was discretised using R3D4 elements.

To save computational time, the number of cohesive elements should be minimised. Hence, this type of element was only defined in certain areas to allow delamination. In particular, they were placed between “skin member 1” and “skin member 2”, as well as in the middle of the ribs (i.e. the resin between two “skin member 1”). In addition, another cohesive zone was defined after the first ply of the “skin member 2”, based on experimental observations. A representation of the distribution of the different elements along the cross-section of the panel is illustrated in Fig.3.

Figure 3: Distribution of different elements in the FE model

With regards to the boundary conditions, the bottom 40 mm of the front and rear surfaces were fully constrained, as well as the bottom surfaces, to reproduce the conditions shown in Fig. 2. A constant velocity of 2 m/s (i.e. much higher than the loading rate from the experimental test) was applied to the reference point on the rigid pole to reduce the computational time. The validity of this approach was checked, according to the following conditions: (i) the applied velocity was not greater than 1% of the speed of sound in the material; (ii) the total kinetic energy did not exceed 10% of the value of the total internal energy. Finally, the interaction between the cylindrical indenter and the sandwich structure was introduced as a general contact with tangential behaviour and a friction coefficient of 0.2. A representation of the two numerical models is illustrated in Fig. 4, where the pole has not been included to have a better view of the cross-sectional area of the structures.

Figure 4: Representation of the FE models for: (a) structure loaded on top of one CFRP rib; (b) structure loaded between two CFRP ribs

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Experimental results

The indentation was stopped after the pole penetrated the specimen by 45 mm. Both configurations exhibited a similar response during the test: (i) delamination of the top and bottom plies at an indenter displacement around 1 mm, which led to large delaminated areas on both sides of the specimens; (ii) fibre breakage became visible under the pole during the tests at an indenter displacement around 8 mm and further delamination was observed in a second weak interface (between both “skin members”). Furthermore, no debonding was visible between the foam core and the composite skins away from the indented area, i.e. the separation did not extend to the edges of the samples. The top view of one of the post-test specimens is illustrated in Fig. 5, where it is observed how the interfacial failure between the core and the skins did not propagate towards the edges of the structure. In addition, Fig. 6 shows the state of the specimens at different indenter displacements for both cases.

Figure 5: Top view of the post-test specimen loaded between two CFRP ribs

Figure 6: Response of the sandwich structures during the mixed-mode tests at an indenter displacement of: (a) 1 mm; (b) 8 mm; (c) 20 mm

With regards to the load-displacement response, a comparison between both configurations is illustrated in Fig. 7. From the graph, it is observed how the specimens which were loaded on top of the rib exhibited a very similar behaviour when compared to the samples loaded in between two ribs. The main difference between those two cases was the slight discrepancy in the slope of the region before the plateau, which seemed to be caused by the extra stiffness of the rib.

Figure 7: Load-displacement response of the two configurations of the sandwich structure

3.2 Correlation between experimental tests and numerical models

The first case that was numerically analysed was the specimen with the load applied directly on a carbon fibre rib. A comparison between experimental and predicted the load-displacement curves for this configuration is shown in Fig. 8. It was found that the oscillations in the numerical results were caused by the loss of contact between the pole and the composite skins, due to element deletion after failure. Therefore, only the peaks should be considered. Final correlations between experimental tests and the FE models are illustrated in Fig. 9 for both configurations. Excellent agreement was found for all cases, validating the predictions from a quantitative point of view.

Figure 8: Load-displacement correlation between tests and FE model of the sandwich structure loaded on top of a CFRP rib

Figure 9: Final load-displacement correlations between tests and FE models of the sandwich structure: (a) loaded on one CFRP rib; (b) loaded between two CFRP ribs

The ability of the FE model to reproduce the deformed shape and failure sequence (i.e. delamination of the top and bottom plies, followed by fibre breakage and further delamination under the indenter) was also assessed. A comparison between tests and numerical predictions is illustrated in Fig. 10 at two different indenter displacements, representing the two clear stages experienced by the specimens. Since the tests exhibited the same response for both configurations, only one configuration is shown in Fig. 10. Again, good agreement was found, qualitatively validating the FE model of this

structure.

Figure 10: Comparison of the deformed shape between tests and FE at an indenter displacement of: (a) 1 mm; (b) 20 mm

3.3 Further studies using Finite Element Analysis

Once the numerical models were validated, Finite Element Analysis was used to assess the extent of the predicted debonding between the foam core and the composite skins, since this feature could not be studied during the tests. To do so, Fig. 11 illustrates the undeformed shape of the cohesive elements on this interface for both configurations, where the red region represents the area which experienced separation between core and face sheets. It was found that the vertical extent of the debonded area was 12 mm larger for the structure loaded between two ribs, whereas in the horizontal direction the extent was similar for both cases (75 mm and 76 mm, respectively).

Figure 11: Debonding between foam core and composite skin predicted by the FE models: (a) structure with one rib; (b) structure with two ribs

Furthermore, the energy absorption capability of the sandwich structure was also studied by integrating the area under the load-displacement curve. Since the tests were conducted at quasi-static rates and there was no final failure, the energy absorbed by each configuration was considered for a pole displacement of 45 mm. Table 1 summarises the values determined from both experimental results and numerical predictions, showing excellent agreement. Then, from the FE models. It was

possible to assess the contribution of each individual part of the structure (i.e. foam core, composite skins and cohesive elements) to the total energy absorbed by the component. These results are presented in Table 2, where it is observed that the majority of the energy was absorbed by the composite material.

Structure	Energy absorption from tests (J)	Energy absorption from FE (J)	Difference (%)
One rib	1,679± 47	1,729	3
Two ribs	1,627± 21	1,569	4

Table 1: Comparison of the energy absorbed by the sandwich structure between experimental tests and FE models

Structure	Energy absorbed by foam (J)	Energy absorbed by CFRP (J)	Energy absorbed by cohesive (J)
One rib	91	1,620	18
Two ribs	105	1,445	18

Table 2: Energy absorbed by the different materials involved in the sandwich structures, extracted from the FE models

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

The response of two sandwich structures was studied under mixed-mode loading conditions. The components consisted of a polymeric foam core sandwiched between composite skins, including one or two carbon fibre ribs. These specimens were loaded by displacing a cylindrical pole at quasi-static rates, trying to emulate conditions from the side-pole impact tests at a lower speed. The main goal was to assess their performance, to study their failure sequence and to develop Finite Element models capable of predicting accurate results.

From the experimental tests, it was found that both configurations followed the same features: delamination of the top and bottom plies of the composite skin, followed by further delamination along a second weak interface between the composite “skin members” and fibre breakage under the indenter. Furthermore, similar load-displacement responses were recorded for both cases.

Numerical results correlated well with the experimental ones with regards to failure mechanisms, load-displacement curves and energy absorption. In addition, FEA was employed to assess the extent of the separation between the core and the composite skins. Finally, the numerical models were also used to study the individual contribution of the three elements of the sandwich panel to the overall energy absorbed by the structure, with the carbon fibre absorbing most of the energy.

These experimental studies and correlations with Finite Element models provided important information about the response of these complex structures, validating the methodology to create accurate numerical models. The outcomes of these studies will be used to design an impact test based on similar mixed-mode loading conditions.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was supported by the EPSRC, the University of Surrey and McLaren Automotive Ltd. We also thank Mr Haynes, who greatly assisted the experimental campaign.

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